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USING THE MOST MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article discusses the use of modern teaching methods and methods in teaching English.*

Key words: *Foreign language, game, education, lesson, innovative technology, technological tools.*

As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is of great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, the world community strives to take its rightful place in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. my future the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our developing nation there is no need to evaluate" 2012 as a logical continuation of this opinion Adopted on December 10, "Further the system of teaching foreign languages "On Improvement Measures" President Karon has expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. textbooks for students of general education schools and vocational colleges were created in accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. It is divided into fam to it aspect (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking) and separate

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understanding and skills are given for each of them.

It also implies increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. For example, for listening comprehension, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. In this, the student at the same time observes the speaker's pronunciation and grammatical rules. , it is required to pay attention to vocabulary and its meanings. It is an important factor for students to know and be able to use information and communication technologies when using modern technologies in the educational process. Teaching a foreign language using modern technologies and learning is one of the most effective ways to teach English The role of teaching through various games is incomparable. Playing various games during the lesson increases the passion for learning science in the classroom, it encourages passive students to participate better in the lessons, students in the classroom Competition between students also creates a team atmosphere. It also increases students' respect for their teachers.

This game is a quick study but gives students some time to think. To play O winm you need a kopto keha And all the students have to stand in the form of दौरा You have to choose a topic For example Things found in a kitchen, food profession, etc. The game starts by throwing the ball to a student. That student says an English

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word about the topic and throws the ball to the next student. Each student who receives the ball says something about the topic. will have to speak. If they repeat the word they were told or can't find the word within a few seconds, they leave the game and sit back and watch the game Don't worry, they will still be learning

Currently, it is known that interactive methods are used in conducting interactive training. In the future, it is desirable that these methods grow to a certain extent into interactive technology. In our opinion, the difference between the concepts of interactive method and technology

The interactive educational method is implemented by each teacher according to the available tools and at the level of his capabilities. In this, each student learns to a different degree according to his motivations and intellectual level. Interactive educational technology - every a teacher ensures that all students learn as intended. In this case, each student, with his own motivation and intellectual level, learns the training at the level foreseen:

Interactive training, based on the study of some experiences of practical application, the quality of these trainings and we can show some factors that influence the increase of efficiency. They can be conditionally called organizational-pedagogical, scientific-methodical and factors related to the teacher, students, and educational tools. we must assume that it will have a positive or negative effect. There are many types of interactive training, they are selected in accordance with the features of the subject of the lesson and the intended goals, and they are prepared accordingly. Learning the necessary knowledge for active participation in the team, readiness for communication, working in mutual cooperation, independent thinking, the ability to express and defend one's opinion

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freely, etc., are essential skills.

For this, it is necessary to correctly select the necessary tools, prepare them, and clearly define the tasks of the trainers and staff. There are specific differences between interactive methods and traditional teaching methods, and each teacher should compare these differences, their advantages and disadvantages in relation to each other when choosing lesson planning and delivery methods. It is necessary to take into account the importance of imparting new knowledge, forming skills, developing and strengthening them, repeating knowledge, applying it in practice, and taking into account the characteristics of the subject, it is most appropriate for training on each subject. It involves the correct selection of interactive or other methods. The use of correctly selected methods ensures that the training is interesting and effective. The current stage of development of educational technology is characterized by the widespread use of interactive teaching methods in the educational process. The uniformity of the teaching technology used for many years is the hegemony of the teacher in the educational process, the teacher accepts the subject without much observation. The attempt to present to the students by bringing them to the level that can be done reduced the activity of the students and began to prevent them from forming the skills of creative thinking. That is why there is an increased attempt to apply interactive lesson methods to the educational process, which do not teach the student, but teach him to learn to read. it will achieve its goal only if it skillfully uses the methods in its place. As a result of using innovative methods in English classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and accurate

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answers is formed. The student strives to be thoroughly prepared for the lessons turns into an active subject of the process. The educational system aims to educate a free-thinking, competent, mature person In the future, we future teachers are innovative We can contribute by developing better ways to use technology more effectively.

List of used literature:

1. Bekmuratova UB Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in English language teaching" Tashkent-2012
2. Oraboeva MP Modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching use and its effectiveness

